

The Influence of Knowledge, Work Quality, and Commitment on Performance through Job Satisfaction in The Family Assistance Team Accelerating Stunting Reduction in Lamongan Regency

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to determine and analyze the influence of knowledge, work quality, and commitment on performance through job satisfaction in the family assistance team to accelerate stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency. This research has theoretical and practical benefits. The approach used in this research is quantitative. The power collection technique used a questionnaire distributed via an online form to the Family Assistance Team of 354 respondents from a total population of 3,108 people. Testing was carried out using the SEM-AMOS statistical technique on the 10 proposed hypotheses. The research results show that: (1) Knowledge influences performance, (2) Work quality influences performance, (3) Commitment influences performance, (4) Knowledge influences job satisfaction, (5) Work quality influences job satisfaction, (6) Commitment influences job satisfaction, (7) Job satisfaction influences performance, (8) Knowledge influences performance through job satisfaction, (9) work quality influences performance through job satisfaction, and (10) Commitment influences performance through satisfaction the work of the Family Assistance Team to accelerate the reduction of stunting in Lamongan Regency.

KEYWORDS: Family Assistance Team, Stunting, Knowledge, Work Quality, Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The 2020-2024 Medium Term Development Plan (RPJMN) has designated stunting as a national issue with a target to reduce it from 24.4% in 2021 to 14% in 2024. Stunting is one of the factors that influence the quality of Human Resources towards Superior Human Resources because Stunting can hinder the growth and development of toddlers starting from the preconception period up to the first 1000 days of life, which affects physical growth and brain development. Stunting is a disruption in the growth and development of children due to chronic malnutrition and recurrent infections, which is characterized by their body length or height being below the standards set by the minister who handles government affairs in the health sector (Presidential Regulation Number 72 of 2021).

Therefore, coordination is needed in all related ministries/institutions, provincial, district/city governments, and village/district governments to be able to integrate, synchronize, and synergize programs and activities to accelerate stunting reduction in a complete, comprehensive, and integrated manner. One of them is by implementing assistance for families at risk of stunting, accompanying all prospective brides/prospective couples of childbearing age (PUS), and surveillance of families at risk of stunting by the Family Assistance Team (TPK). The Family Assistance Team (TPK) is a group of staff formed and consisting of Midwives, Cadres TP. PKK and family planning cadres to carry out assistance including counseling, facilitation of referral services, and facilitation of acceptance of social assistance programs for prospective brides/prospective couples of childbearing age, pregnant women, postpartum mothers, children aged 0-59 months as well as conducting surveillance of families at risk of stunting for early detection risk factors for stunting. In various conditions, the composition of the Family Assistance Team can be adjusted through collaboration with Midwives from other villages/districts or involving nurses or other health workers. (BKKBN, 2021).

Lamongan Regency is one of the districts in East Java Province that has a fairly large stunting problem. According to the results of the 2022 Indonesian Nutrition Status Survey (SSGI), the prevalence of stunting in Lamongan Regency is 27.5%. Higher than the prevalence of stunting in East Java Province, namely 19.2% and 21.6% nationally. The prevalence of stunting in Lamongan Regency increased by 7% from the results of the Indonesian Nutrition Status Survey in the previous year, namely 20.5% in 2021. This has resulted in the Lamongan Regency Government becoming increasingly diligent in several programs and activities in efforts to accelerate stunting reduction, one of which is by optimizing performance. Family Support Team Cadre.

Research conducted by Abebe Negeri and Quan Ji (2023) concluded that knowledge and commitment have a significant positive effect on employee performance. In line with that, Sunyoto, et.al (2023) also found in their research that knowledge has a significant

The Influence of Knowledge, Work Quality, and Commitment on Performance through Job Satisfaction in The Family Assistance Team Accelerating Stunting Reduction in Lamongan Regency

positive effect on performance both with and without intervening variables, namely the ability to innovate. In completing work targets, sufficient knowledge is needed to solve problems quickly, precisely, and accurately so that the tasks given are carried out well and according to expectations or what has been planned.

Diana, et.al (2022) concluded in their research that commitment has a positive effect on performance, employees who are committed will always provide the best performance in their work. Xuelin Bu, et.al (2022) in their research in Pakistan concluded that employee engagement and work-life satisfaction have a significant effect on performance. Likewise, research conducted by Komar, et.al (2021) showed that compensation and quality of work life had a significant effect on employee performance. In this case, the Family Assistance Team accelerates stunting reduction, which has its feeling of satisfaction when carrying out assistance activities for families and getting a good response from the community and appreciation from superiors for what has been completed will improve the performance of the Family Assistance Team with a more diligent and routine attitude. Assist and routinely carry out recording and reporting of activities.

Based on the research results above, development was carried out through this research to look at exogenous variables, namely performance with 3 (three) endogenous variables, and provide intervening ones. Therefore, this research aims to determine the influence of knowledge, work quality, and commitment on performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable in the Family Assistance Team to accelerate stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency.

II. THEORETICAL STUDY

A. AMO (Ability, Motivation, Opportunity)

AMO theory explains the factors that encourage Human Resources to improve performance, namely Ability (A), Motivation (M), and Opportunity to Participate (O). AMO theory implies that human resource management has the function of meeting employees' needs for abilities and skills as well as motivation to use their abilities in various roles. Employees will perform if they have the necessary abilities and are motivated to improve their performance if they get the opportunity for self-actualization. Blumberg & Pringle (1982) developed the AMO model, namely that performance is a function of capacity to perform (including variables of age, knowledge, education level, and energy level), willingness to perform (including variables of motivation, job satisfaction, personality, values, and expectations), and opportunity to perform (including variables of working conditions, equipment, materials, leader behavior, procedures and time) and shows three elements of performance, namely: opportunity, capacity and willingness.

B. Knowledge

Knowledge is a recording of what humans see, hear, and feel which then forms a reaction to an event so that an attitude or impact arises on it, either positive or negative. Knowledge or erudition is the result of human sensing or the result of a person's knowledge of an object through his or her five senses. When sensing to produce knowledge it is influenced by the intensity of attention and perception of an object. A person's knowledge is mostly obtained through the sense of hearing and the sense of sight (Notoatmodjo, 2014). According to Pesiwarissa (2008), knowledge indicators are as follows:

1. Employee placement is adjusted to the employee's educational background
2. Employee placement is adjusted to knowledge insight about the job
3. The knowledge that supports the implementation of work.

C. Work Quality

Marcana (2000) states that what is meant by work quality is: "Work quality is a form of behavior or activities carried out by expectations and needs or goals to be achieved effectively and efficiently". According to Ashari et.al (2020: 186), it is said that an indicator of work quality is a result that can be measured by the effectiveness and efficiency of work carried out by human resources or other resources in achieving the company's goals or objectives well and efficiently.

A. Commitment

Work commitment can be defined as a person's level of willingness and attachment to the organization where he works. This definition includes the concepts of loyalty, responsibility, attachment, and dedication to the organization. According to Mowday, Porter, and Steers (1982), work commitment is a psychological attitude consisting of three dimensions, namely affective, normative, and continuity. Affective is a commitment that arises from positive feelings towards the organization, normative is a commitment that arises from moral obligations or norms to continue working in the organization, and continuity is a commitment that arises from the costs that must be incurred if you leave the organization. Meyer and Allen (1991) formulated three dimensions of commitment in organizations, namely: affective, continuance, and normative.

B. Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an ideal condition that must be achieved. According to Robbins (2002: 36), job satisfaction is an individual's general attitude towards their work. Someone with a high attitude of satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards work, and

The Influence of Knowledge, Work Quality, and Commitment on Performance through Job Satisfaction in The Family Assistance Team Accelerating Stunting Reduction in Lamongan Regency

someone who is dissatisfied with their job shows a negative attitude towards it. Indicators used to measure job satisfaction according to Luthans (2011) include the job itself, salary, promotions, coworkers, and supervision.

C. Performance

Performance is a measure of the success of a plan that has been realized. Good performance is proven by achieving predetermined targets or expectations, either meeting or exceeding targets. According to Robbins and Coulter (2007), performance is a person's level of success in achieving predetermined goals, both in terms of quantity and quality. In connection with the measurement of work performance assessment, employee performance, according to Simamora (2004), is measured by the following indicators:

1. Quantity of work output, which includes the amount of production activities produced.
2. The quality of work results, which includes the conformity of production activities concerning the provisions that apply as standards for the process of implementing activities and organizational plans.
3. Timeliness of work completion, namely compliance with the time required or expected in carrying out activities.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the introduction and literature review described previously, the research conceptual framework can be described as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The hypothesis proposed is:

H1 : Knowledge influences the performance of the Family Assistance Team to accelerate stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency

H2 : The quality of work influences the performance of the Family Assistance Team to accelerate stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency

H3 : Commitment influences the performance of the Family Assistance Team to accelerate stunting reduction In Lamongan Regency

H4 : Job knowledge influences the job satisfaction of the Family Assistance Team, accelerating the decline stunting in Lamongan Regency

H5 : The quality of work influences the job satisfaction of the Family Assistance Team, accelerating the decline stunting in Lamongan Regency

H6 : Work commitment influences the job satisfaction of the Family Support Team and accelerates the decline stunting in Lamongan Regency

H7 : Job satisfaction as an intervening influence on the performance of the accelerated Family Assistance Team reducing stunting in Lamongan Regency

H8 : Knowledge influences performance through job satisfaction in the Family Assistance Team acceleration of stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency

H9 : Work quality influences performance through job satisfaction in the Family Assistance Team acceleration of stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency

H10: Work commitment influences performance through job satisfaction in the Family Assistance Team acceleration of stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency

The Influence of Knowledge, Work Quality, and Commitment on Performance through Job Satisfaction in The Family Assistance Team Accelerating Stunting Reduction in Lamongan Regency

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Data Types and Sources

This research is descriptive explanatory causal research that will explain the causal relationship between exogenous variables (knowledge, work quality, and commitment) on endogenous variables (performance) and intervening variables (job satisfaction). This research uses a questionnaire structure with a five-point Likert scale for primary data collection, then the data obtained will be analyzed using the AMOS SEM statistical technique.

B. Population

The population is the group of subjects to whom the generalization of research results is intended. The population of this study was the Family Assistance Team to accelerate the stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency, totaling 3,108 people. Meanwhile, the sample used as respondents was 354.

C. Data Collection

The data collection technique used was a questionnaire distributed to respondents using Google Forms.

D. Data Analysis Method

Data analysis in this research uses the SEM AMOS (Structural Equation Modeling Analysis Moment of Structural) analysis method which can provide a simultaneous analysis process related to the multivariate research model. SEM AMOS is a statistical tool used to solve multilevel models simultaneously that cannot be solved by linear regression equations and makes it possible to determine, estimate, assess, and create models or path diagrams to show hypothesized relationships between variables. This test is done by analyzing the Regression Weight value, namely the Critical Ratio value (CR and Probability (P)). The required limits are ≥ 1.96 for the CR value and ≤ 0.05 for the P value. If the data processing results show a value that meets these requirements, then the research hypothesis proposed can be accepted. Before arriving at hypothesis testing, a validity test is carried out first, namely, the dimension indicators can be shown with several conditions that are used as significant validity if they can fulfill these conditions.

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation of Measurement Model Fit

The measurement model analysis was carried out simultaneously on all constructs, the estimation results of which are presented in Figure 2.

Figure. 2 Measurement Model Fit

The Influence of Knowledge, Work Quality, and Commitment on Performance through Job Satisfaction in The Family Assistance Team Accelerating Stunting Reduction in Lamongan Regency

The results of the measurement model suitability test according to Figure 5.1 are presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Fit Measure in the Measurement Model

Fit Measure		Critical Value	Measurement Model	
			Index value	Keterangan
Absolute Fit Indices	Prob. χ^2 ^(a)	> 0,05	0,000	Even a good fit
	Cmin/df	≤ 3,00	1,776	Good fit
	GFI	≥ 0,90	0,949	Good fit
	RMSEA	≤ 0,08	0,047	Good fit
	SRMR	≤ 0,08	0,031	Good fit
Incremental Fit Indices	CFI	≥ 0,95	0,980	Good fit
	TLI	≥ 0,95	0,974	Good fit
	NFI	≥ 0,90	0,957	Good fit
	RFI	≥ 0,90	0,942	Good fit
Parsimony Fit Indices	AGFI	≥ 0,90	0,922	Good fit

^(a) In a model with a sample size of $n > 250$ or several indicators more than 30 ($m > 30$), the model is still fit even though the value *probability* is below 0.05 or even a good fit. (Hair et al., 2014:584).

Source: SEM AMOS Output

Table 1 shows that the results of the suitability test on the measurement model have produced good suitability criteria, both absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices, and parsimony fit indices, all criteria have met the requirements. Thus the measurement model has a good and acceptable model fit.

After ensuring the measurement model has a good model fit, then construct validity testing is carried out. Construct validity shows a test to determine the extent to which indicators measure the construct. In SEM, construct validity testing is carried out through convergent validity, with the rule of thumb that a construct is said to meet convergent validity if the indicators on the construct have a standardized regression weight (factor loading) value of at least 0.50 and a preferable value of 0.70. (Hair et al., 2014:632).

Table 2. Construct Validity Test

Construct	Indicator	Factor Loading	Information
Knowledge (X1)	TPK Duties and Roles (X1.1)	0.844	Valid
	Suitability of Program Field (X1.2)	0.796	Valid
	Education and Training (X1.3)	0.783	Valid
Work Quality (X2)	Time Efficiency (X2.1)	0.879	Valid
	Effectiveness (X2.2)	0.818	Valid
Commitment (X3)	Affective Commitment (X3.1)	0.846	Valid
	Continuing Commitment (X3.2)	0.730	Valid
	Normative Commitment (X3.3)	0.874	Valid
Job Satisfaction (Z)	Salary (Z.1)	0.570	Valid
	Supervision (Z.2)	0.757	Valid
	Coworkers (Z.3)	0.777	Valid
	TPK Work (Z.4)	0.828	Valid
Performance (Y)	Quantity (Y.1)	0.919	Valid
	Quality (Y.2)	0.765	Valid
	Timeliness (Y.3)	0.855	Valid

Source: SEM AMOS Output

The results of the construct validity evaluation in Table 2 show that in the measurement model, all indicators produce factor loading values greater than 0.50, so these indicators are declared valid in forming the constructs of knowledge, work quality, commitment, job satisfaction, and performance, so that meets convergent validity.

The results of the construct reliability evaluation for each construct can be seen in Table 3 below:

The Influence of Knowledge, Work Quality, and Commitment on Performance through Job Satisfaction in The Family Assistance Team Accelerating Stunting Reduction in Lamongan Regency

Table 3. Construct Reliability Test

Variable	Construct Reliability	AVE	Information
Knowledge (X1)	0.849	0.653	Reliable
Work Quality (X2)	0.838	0.721	Reliable
Commitment (X3)	0.859	0.671	Reliable
Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.826	0.547	Reliable
Performance (Y)	0.885	0.720	Reliable
Rule of thumbs	≥ 0.70	≥ 0.50	

Source: SEM AMOS Output

Table 3 shows that each variable produces a construct reliability value greater than 0.70 and also an AVE value greater than 0.50, so it can be concluded that the indicators that measure the constructs of knowledge, work quality, commitment, job satisfaction, and performance, are declared reliable or reliable.

B. Evaluation of Structural Model Fit

Figure 3. Structural Model Fit

The structural model stage begins with an evaluation of the structural model fit (goodness of fit) which functions to ensure the model developed is by the data (fit). The results of calculating the values of the goodness of fit indices produced by the structural model are the results of the suitability test of the structural model showing that all the criteria for absolute fit indices, incremental fit indices, and parsimony fit indices meet the requirements (good fit). Thus the structural model can be accepted. Good fit means the model developed in this research provides a good fit to the empirical data, while marginal fit means the model fit is within acceptable limits.

Similar to regression analysis, SEM also produces an output coefficient of determination (R^2). Hair et al. (2014:152) state that the coefficient of determination measures the proportion of diversity in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variable. The results of calculating the coefficient of determination (R^2) of the influence between variables in this study show that the RZ^2 value is 0.713, meaning that the percentage of influence of work knowledge, work quality, and work commitment on job satisfaction in the TPK for accelerating stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency is 71.3 percent. , while the remaining 28.7 percent is influenced by other variables. Furthermore, the RY^2 value is 0.737, meaning that the percentage influence of knowledge, work quality, commitment, and job satisfaction on the TPK performance in accelerating stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency is 73.7 percent, while the remaining 26.3 percent is influenced by other variables.

The value of the total coefficient of determination (R^2 total) is known to be 0.725, this shows that the model developed in this research can explain around 72.5 percent of the diversity of the data. In another sense, the model in this research has very good

The Influence of Knowledge, Work Quality, and Commitment on Performance through Job Satisfaction in The Family Assistance Team Accelerating Stunting Reduction in Lamongan Regency

predictive relevance or is relevant to be used to predict cadre performance through knowledge, work quality, commitment, and job satisfaction.

C. Hypothesis Testing: Direct and Indirect Effect Analysis

The following are the results of direct influence testing for testing each direct influence hypothesis knowledge, quality of work, and commitment to job satisfaction and performance at the TPK to accelerate stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency.

Table 4. Testing the Direct Effect Hypothesis

Direct Influence	Std. Estimate	CR	P-value	Hypothetical Decisions
Knowledge (X1) → Performance (Y)	0.202	3,433	0.007	H1 Accepted
Work Quality (X2) → Performance (Y)	0.361	4,341	0.012	H2 Accepted
Commitment (X3) → Performance (Y)	0.236	3,194	0.021	H3 Accepted
Knowledge (X1) → Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.323	5,766	0.006	H4 Accepted
Work Quality (X2) → Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.361	4,261	0.003	H5 Accepted
Commitment (X3) → Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.397	6,135	0.013	H6 Accepted
Job Satisfaction (Z) → Performance (Y)	0.258	2,220	0.019	H7 Accepted
CR and the p-value are calculated using the bootstrap bias-corrected percentile method approach				

Source: SEM AMOS Output

Based on Table 4 above, it can be explained as follows:

1. The coefficient estimation results for the influence of knowledge on performance show a significant influence with a CR value of 3.433 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (p-value) of 0.007 (smaller than the 5% significance level). The resulting influence coefficient is 0.202 (positive), meaning that the higher the cadre's work knowledge, the higher their performance will be. This is by previous research conducted by Sunyoto, et.al (2023) which stated that knowledge management has a positive effect on performance. Also supported by research from Abu-Mahfouz, et.al (2023) and Nuel, et.al (2023) which state the same thing, namely that working knowledge has a positive effect on performance. For cadres of the Family Assistance Team in the program to accelerate stunting reduction, work knowledge is very much needed for the Family Assistance Team in carrying out their roles and duties in providing assistance, counseling, and IEC to target families at risk of stunting as well as skills in carrying out the administration of recording and reporting activities that have been carried out well. offline and online via the Elsimil application.

2. The results of this research regarding the influence of work quality on performance show a significant influence with a CR value of 4.341 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (p-value) of 0.012 (smaller than the 5% significance level). The resulting influence coefficient is 0.361 (positive), meaning that the higher the quality of the work of the Family Assistance Team cadres, the higher their performance will be. This supports research conducted by Komar, et.al (2021) and Xuelin Bu, et.al (2022), namely that the quality of work life has a significant effect on employee performance. According to Wilson and Heyel (1987: 101) "Quality of work shows the extent to which the quality of an employee in carrying out his duties includes accuracy, completeness and neatness" which is also influenced by the burden of responsibility, compensation, working environment conditions with colleagues and superiors.

This time the quality of work is determined by indicators of the efficiency and effectiveness of the work of the Family Assistance Team because apart from being a Family Assistance Team, the person concerned has other responsibilities that are inherent in being an element of the Family Assistance Team. So the more they can utilize their time and manage their work well, the more their performance will improve. Although there is other research conducted by Diana, et.al (2022) in her research entitled Creating the Path for Quality of Work Life: A Study on Nurse Performance which found that the quality of work life has no effect on performance, which happens because employees work to get compensation in the form of a salary or other income and they need it. Not because of feelings of pride, happiness, or having that job.

3. As with previous research conducted by Abebe Negeri and Quan Ji (2023), which states that commitment has a significant positive effect on performance, the results of this research also confirm that the effect of commitment on performance shows a significant influence with a CR value of 3.194 (greater than 1.96) and a significance value (p-value) of 0.021 (smaller than the 5% significance level). The resulting influence coefficient is 0.236 (positive), meaning that the stronger the cadre's commitment, the higher their performance will be. Organizational commitment is a condition where an individual has trust, attachment, and a feeling of belonging to the company so that the individual will prioritize the interests of the organization over individual interests. Even Diana, et.al (2022) and Le Thi Minh Loan (2020) stated this in their research.

Stunting is a national priority program whose target is to reduce it to 14% by 2024 and is a commitment of all government agencies, from the central to regional and village levels. This also increases the commitment of the Family Assistance Team due to policy and budget support from government officials. Meanwhile, another commitment emerged from the enthusiasm of the Family Assistance Team in reducing stunting rates in their respective villages.

The Influence of Knowledge, Work Quality, and Commitment on Performance through Job Satisfaction in The Family Assistance Team Accelerating Stunting Reduction in Lamongan Regency

Based on Table 5, it can be explained as follows:

1. SEM AMOS statistical test results for an indirect path or X1 mediation $\rightarrow Z \rightarrow Y$ show a significant effect with a coefficient value of 0.083 (positive) a CR value of 2.024 (≥ 1.96) and a p-value of 0.022 ($\leq 5\%$). Thus, job satisfaction significantly mediates the influence of knowledge on the performance of TPK cadres in accelerating stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency (H8 is accepted). The nature of the mediator is partial mediation, meaning that improving the performance of TPK cadres can only be done by increasing their work knowledge, but if you also focus on increasing job satisfaction, the performance of TPK cadres will increase. Hypothesis 8 and following hypothesis 9 according to the test results are accepted or significantly positive. These two hypotheses are the latest from the research carried out this time.
2. SEM AMOS statistical test results for an indirect path or X2 mediation $\rightarrow Z \rightarrow Y$ also show a significant effect with a coefficient value of 0.093 (positive) a CR value of 2.000 (≥ 1.96) and a p-value of 0.010 ($\leq 5\%$). Thus, job satisfaction also significantly mediates the influence of work quality on the performance of TPK cadres in accelerating stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency (H9 is accepted). The nature of the mediator is partial mediation, meaning that improving the performance of TPK cadres can only be done by improving the quality of their work, but if they also focus on job satisfaction, the performance of TPK cadres will increase. It is hoped that by knowing, the Family Assistance Team will work with good quality, resulting in job satisfaction and having an impact on increasing performance for the stunting reduction acceleration program in Lamongan Regency.
3. Commitment is an employee's feeling of attachment or psychological and physical connection to their work, while job satisfaction is an ideal condition that must be achieved. This is because employees' attitudes and feelings towards all aspects of their work environment will influence their attitudes and behavior in carrying out the tasks given. If employees can carry out their duties well then the employee will achieve satisfaction at work. In Hypothesis 3 and Hypothesis 6, it has been explained that there is a significant positive influence between commitment to performance and commitment to job satisfaction. In the results of hypothesis testing 10, the indirect path or mediation is X3 $\rightarrow Z \rightarrow Y$ also shows a significant effect with a coefficient value of 0.102 (positive) a CR value of 2.083 (≥ 1.96) and a p-value of 0.021 ($\leq 5\%$). Thus, job satisfaction also significantly mediates the effect of commitment on performance among TPK cadres in accelerating stunting reduction in the Lamongan Regency (H10 is accepted). The nature of the mediator is partial mediation, meaning that improving the performance of TPK cadres can only be done by strengthening their commitment, but if you also focus on increasing job satisfaction, then the performance of TPK cadres will increase. This is the same as research conducted by Le Thi Minh Loan (2020) and N. Nurlina (2022), namely that work commitment has a significant positive effect on performance through job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Stunting is a disruption in the growth and development of children due to chronic malnutrition and recurrent infections, which is characterized by their body length or height being below the standards set by the minister who handles government affairs in the health sector. Stunting is a national priority program that is targeted to reduce the prevalence rate to 14% in 2024. To implement this, one of the ways is to form a management workforce through the Family Assistance Team.

The Family Assistance Team (TPK) is a group of staff formed and consisting of Midwives, Cadres TP. PKK and family planning cadres to carry out assistance including counseling, facilitation of referral services, and facilitation of acceptance of social assistance programs for prospective brides/prospective couples of childbearing age, pregnant women, postpartum mothers, children aged 0-59 months as well as conducting surveillance of families at risk of stunting for early detection risk factors for stunting. The Family Assistance Team has a work and reporting mechanism by the direction of the supervisory agency, and in this case, it will be the object of research to determine the influence of several variables on the performance of the Family Assistance Team.

There are 7 direct hypotheses from 3 independent variables (X), 1 intervening variable (Z), and 1 dependent variable (Y) with the hypothesis test results being significantly positive or accepted. Namely: the effect of knowledge on performance (H1), the effect of work quality on performance (H2), the effect of commitment on performance (H3), the effect of knowledge on job satisfaction (H4), the effect of work quality on job satisfaction (H5), the effect of commitment on satisfaction work (H6), and the influence of job satisfaction on performance (H7). This means that all variables X and Variable Z in the Family Assistance Team influence the performance carried out for the stunting reduction acceleration program in Lamongan Regency.

There are 3 indirect hypotheses, the independent variables (knowledge, quality, and commitment) through the intervening variable (job satisfaction) on the performance variable with the results of the hypothesis test being significantly positive or accepted. Namely the influence of knowledge through job satisfaction on performance (H8), the influence of work quality through job satisfaction on performance (H9), and the influence of commitment through job satisfaction on performance (10). The positive significant test results mean that these three variables can independently improve performance, but if they are added to job satisfaction they will further improve performance, and this applies to the Family Assistance Team.

The results of the total effect analysis of the AMOS SEM statistical test provide implications regarding the priority scale in efforts to improve the performance of the Family Assistance Team to accelerate the stunting reduction in the Lamongan Regency, starting

The Influence of Knowledge, Work Quality, and Commitment on Performance through Job Satisfaction in The Family Assistance Team Accelerating Stunting Reduction in Lamongan Regency

from the highest priority to the lowest. Namely, the performance of the Family Assistance Team is driven more by work quality, then work commitment, work knowledge, and finally work satisfaction.

The latest in this research are hypothesis 8 and hypothesis 9, namely the influence of knowledge through job satisfaction on performance and the influence of work quality through job satisfaction on performance. Researchers have limitations in accessing previous research regarding these results so Hypothesis 8 and Hypothesis 9 are the latest, which hopefully can add to the body of knowledge in the field of human resource management.

SUGGESTIONS

From the results of this research, several suggestions were obtained, namely:

1. For research objects (Family Assistance Team)

From the results of this research, it can be concluded that the performance of the Family Assistance Team has been good as proven by mastery of knowledge, tasks, and roles as well as activeness in recording and reporting both offline and online via the Elsimil application. What needs to be improved is expanding the range of assistance that is not only to meet the minimum target but comprehensive to all mentoring targets. Intervention and intensification in efforts to prevent stunting through support and coordination with cross-sectors and closest partners involved in the stunting reduction acceleration program.

2. For Stakeholders

The stunting reduction acceleration program is the focus of all government programs, both formal and informal, therefore the seriousness of stakeholders in Lamongan Regency is needed in various aspects such as budget, personnel, legality, and the policies taken.

3. For future research

This research is far from perfect in looking at the performance of the Family Assistance Team from only 4 variables, namely knowledge, quality, commitment, and job satisfaction. Future researchers can deepen it with other variables or add intervening variables and even create moderating variables in their research framework.

ACKNOWLEDGE

This research was carried out without any tendency towards certain interests, this research was carried out to find out the things that influence the performance of the Family Assistance Team to accelerate stunting reduction in Lamongan Regency to prepare a final assignment as a requirement for obtaining a master's degree at the University of 17 August 1945 Surabaya.

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